

A Study on the Fatigue Life Estimation of FRP under Random Loading

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ABSTRACT

An investigation was performed on the fatigue properties of satin woven glass cloth FRP, with special emphases on the effects of input wave type and programmed stress pattern. This paper deals with the fatigue estimation of FRP by means of the r.m.s. peak stress amplitude and the equivalent stress amplitude based upon Miner's rule. Test results showed that the effects of input wave and stress pattern could be explained fairly well with the aid of r.m.s. peak stress value. It was also shown that the fatigue life under the Gaussian narrow band random loads and some other kinds of program loads could be estimated to some extent by an equivalent stress amplitude method. The frequency component of random load applied on the specimen was analyzed by a FFT method. Then, not only the effect of variable stress but also the effect of variable frequency was discussed in this paper.

INTRODUCTION

It is an important problem that the fatigue life of engineering structures subjected to random loads must be accurately estimated so that the fatigue design with safety and reliability can be performed. After investigating the statistical nature of random loads, it is most common for the fatigue life estimation under the random load to be compared with the basic S-N curve. However, such a study has poorer in FRP materials than other materials (1). From this standpoint, this paper dealt with the fatigue life estimations of FRP under various input waves and random loads.

SPECIMEN PREPARATION AND TESTING PROCEDURES

The material consists of polyester resin which is used as matrix and satin woven glass cloth which is used as reinforcement, and was made by means of a hand-lay-up method at room temperature and then cured for four hours at 80°C. After being removed from the oven, it was cut in the direction parallel to the warp of glass fabric in dimension shown in Fig. 1. The pieces were then kept for two days under constant conditions of 23°C and 65% humidity. Table 1 shows the composition of the material tested. In Table 2, the glass fiber content of the specimen and its mechanical properties are shown.

Repeated tension and compression fatigue tests were conducted under both the constant stress and the programmed block type variable amplitudes by a hydraulic fatigue testing machine. All kinds of programmed load and random load waves used in experiment were simulated by the internal function generator.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Effects of Input Wave and Stress Pattern

Investigations were made on the fatigue life of satin woven glass cloth FRP under three kinds of load waves (sinusoidal, triangular and pulse). At least ten specimens were used for each stress level in order to evaluate the dispersion in the fatigue life. Scatter of the data in this paper was analyzed by using a two-parameter Weibull distribution.

Fig. 2 shows S-N diagrams between applied stress and expected fatigue life under various input waves. Each straight line in this figure was calculated by a least square method and these results were shown in Eq.(1) and summarized in Table 3.

$$\sigma^m \cdot N_f = C \tag{1}$$

The fatigue life for the triangular wave was almost equal to that of the sinusoidal wave because of the similar load wave pattern. Whilst, the fatigue life for the pulse wave became remarkably smaller compared with the other cases.

The P-S-N diagram for the different probabilities of failure 5, 10, 50, 90, and 95 percent under the sinusoidal wave is shown in Fig. 3 as an example. The dispersion in the life is the widest at the medium life range (10^5 - 10^6 cycles). As reported in previous paper(2), this wide dispersion of medium life is supposed to be due to complex fracture mechanisms in the fiber-resin interface. And this tendency of dispersion at varying stress level was similar for each wave type.

FRP materials have the nature of visco-elasticity which is highly dependent on time. It is very difficult to make an estimation of the fatigue life under different load waves by means of the maximum stress amplitude, as shown in Fig. 2. Because, the duration subjected to the maximum stress amplitude is different in each wave. Therefore, the fatigue life estimation was carried out here by the r.m.s. peak stress value.

Now, if the random variation on a time t is x(t) and that after the time of τ is x(t+ τ), the autocorrelation function R(τ) is well known to be the functional form of Eq.(2).

$$R(\tau) = E[x(t) \cdot x(t+\tau)] \tag{2}$$

$$= \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \int_{-\frac{T}{2}}^{\frac{T}{2}} x(t) \cdot x(t+\tau) dt$$

The autocorrelation function for $\tau=0$ becomes the following form.

$$R(0) = E[\{x(t)\}^2] = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \int_{-\frac{T}{2}}^{\frac{T}{2}} x^2(t) dt \tag{3}$$

Eq.(3) is called root mean square. The numerical calculation method as shown in Eq.(4) was used to find out the value of R(0) under each actual load wave operating on the test specimen in this study (3).

$$R(0) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \{x_i(t)\}^2 \tag{4}$$

Each r.m.s. peak stress value was calculated by Eq.(4). Fig. 4 shows the S-N curve where the maximum stress amplitude was converted into the r.m.s. peak stress amplitude.

It is clear from this figure that the S-N curve evaluated by the r.m.s. peak

stress may be represented by an approximate straight line for both the sinusoidal wave and the pulse wave. The shape parameter values of the data, α were shown in this figure to indicate the degree of variation. As a result, the stress dependency on fatigue life and its dispersion was similar for both waves. Consequently, the difference of the fatigue life in the both input waves could be explained fairly well with the aid of r.m.s. peak stress value.

Fatigue tests under the simulated program loads were conducted to provide the estimation of the fatigue life based on the above-mentioned r.m.s. peak stress value in the service load. It is generally known that the distribution of peak stress in a Gaussian narrow band random process is approximately represented by Rayleigh distribution. Therefore, the next fatigue test was conducted for such a acting load that the envelope of peak stress of sinusoidal excitation has a probability density function of Rayleigh distribution, as written by the next form (4).

$$a(t) = \sigma \sqrt{-\ln(1 - \frac{t}{T})^2} \sin \omega_0 t \quad (5)$$

Where, the frequency ω_0 was 125.66 rad/sec in this fatigue test, $a(t)$ is the actual stress amplitude and T is the total time of one block.

The values of t/T in Eq.(5) were set as shown in Table 4 and the values of σ were varied to 50, 60, 70 and 80 MPa. Then, the fatigue life tests were carried out under four kinds of programmed load where the Low-High type and the High-Low type were under 8-step loading and the Low-High-Low type and the Random type were under 14-step loading. The photograph in Fig. 5 is the actual program load observed with an oscilloscope and Fig. 6 shows the results of fatigue life under those program loads. It is obvious from this figure that the fatigue life estimation under different load pattern can be made to some extent by r.m.s. peak stress values.

Frequency Dependency of Fatigue Life

In estimating the fatigue life of FRP under the random load, frequency dependency will be one of the most important subject. From this standpoint, the constant stress fatigue test was conducted under the sinusoidal wave with six kinds of frequency (0.1, 1, 5, 10, 15, 20 Hz). As stated in the previous section, scatter of the fatigue life data for each frequency was analyzed by using a two-parameter Weibull distribution. The P-S-N diagram in the case of 1Hz is shown in Fig. 7. The dispersion of fatigue life for all stress levels is a lot smaller than the case of 20Hz as shown in Fig. 3.

Now, let's consider the frequency dependency on fatigue life. The relationship between the applied stress σ and fatigue life N_f is generally represented by Eq.(6). The results for the various frequencies were summarized in Table 5 and S-N diagrams for each frequency is shown in Fig. 8.

$$m \log \sigma + \log N_f = \log C \quad (6)$$

All the S-N lines tend to concentrate on a certain point (σ, N_f) at the long life range (10^7 cycles). In other words, the slopes of these S-N lines appear to change with centering this point. This point was determined from an intersection of the S-N lines of 20Hz and 0.1Hz including the static strength point. It is clear from these results that the fatigue life of FRP is affected strongly by the difference of frequency and the values of constant in Eq.(6) were linear with each frequency under the constant stress amplitude. Hence, Eq.(7) could be obtained by determining both constants of m and $\log C$ by means of a least square method.

$$\sigma^{0.912 f + 9.781} \times N_f = 10^{1.777 f + 25.986} \quad (7)$$

The fatigue life under the different frequencies and stress amplitudes will be approximately calculated by Eq.(7).

Fatigue Life Estimation under Random Loads

Two kinds of the random wave (RW1 and RW2) as shown in Fig. 9 were used for the next fatigue test. Each peak stress value of RW1 has the random numbers generated by the computer (HP-85). The so-called FFT analysis was conducted in order to clarify the statistical nature of random load to be applied on the specimen. The FFT analysis result for RW1 wave, as shown in Fig. 10, revealed that the maximum power spectral density exists in the frequency, 10Hz. RW2 wave is programmed with the sinusoidal waves of frequency, 10Hz to be compared with the fatigue life of RW1 wave contained the other frequency components. And each stress amplitude of RW2 wave is determined identically to peak stress amplitude on the tension side of RW1 wave. Therefore, the fatigue damage of the specimen is supposed to occur under the frequency 10Hz for both waves. The fatigue tests of FRP were carried out in the same way for the maximum power spectral density of the frequency, 20Hz. Fig. 11 shows the S-N diagram of both RW1 wave and RW2 wave which was drawn by using the peak stress amplitude in case of 10Hz. It is obvious from the figure that the fatigue life estimation by the peak stress amplitude are difficult in this case. Then, the consideration will now be given to the validity of evaluating the fatigue life for RW1 wave and RW2 wave with the aid of equivalent stress amplitude which is based upon Miner's rule.

The equivalent stress amplitude σ_{eff} is regarded as the constant stress amplitude according to the Miner's rule (5) and is represented by

$$\sigma_{eff} = \left(\frac{\sum_i n_i \sigma_i^m}{\sum_i n_i} \right)^{\frac{1}{m}} \tag{8}$$

Where, m values for 10Hz and 20Hz used are 19.437 and 27.889 from Table 5. Then, the probability density function of peak stress, $f_p(\sigma)$ can usually be assumed to be a Rayleigh distribution for the narrow band random process as stated in the previous section. Therefore, σ_{eff} is indicated as follows.

$$\sigma_{eff} = \left\{ \frac{\int_0^{\infty} \sigma^m f_p(\sigma) d\sigma}{\int_0^{\infty} f_p(\sigma) d\sigma} \right\}^{\frac{1}{m}} \tag{9}$$

If the r.m.s. peak stress value is represented as σ_{eff} , the function $f_p(\sigma)$ is given by

$$f_p(\sigma) = \frac{2\sigma}{\sigma_{rms}^2} \exp\left(-\frac{\sigma^2}{\sigma_{rms}^2}\right) \tag{10}$$

By substituting Eq.(10) into Eq.(9)

$$\sigma_{eff} = \left\{ \frac{\int_0^{\infty} \sigma^{m+1} e^{-\frac{\sigma^2}{\sigma_{rms}^2}} d\sigma}{\int_0^{\infty} \sigma e^{-\frac{\sigma^2}{\sigma_{rms}^2}} d\sigma} \right\}^{\frac{1}{m}} = \left[\Gamma\left(\frac{m}{2}+1\right) \right]^{\frac{1}{m}} \sigma_{rms} \tag{11}$$

is given (6). As seen from this Eq.(11), the equivalent stress amplitude is considered to be a function of r.m.s. peak stress value. Therefore, the r.m.s. peak stress value seems to be a key point in evaluating the fatigue life of FRP under the narrow band random loading.

Fig. 12 shows S-N diagram in the case of 10Hz, which evaluated the fatigue lives for RW1 wave and RW2 wave respectively by means of the equivalent stress amplitude. The basic S-N line is shown in the figure as a simple approach to estimate the fatigue life. It is clear from this figure that the fatigue life could be estimated well from the basic S-N line by using the equivalent stress amplitude.

As discussed in the previous section, the fatigue life of FRP is influenced considerably by the difference of the frequency component contained in the service load. Most of random loads have various fluctuations on frequency and stress amplitude. Hence, the next fatigue tests were carried out under two kinds of program load as shown in Fig. 13. Type I wave is the program load where the frequency was changed under the constant stress amplitude. Type II wave is the program load where the both frequency and stress amplitude were changed. Table 6 shows the combinations of the frequency and stress amplitude in the actual waves tested. In order to identify the frequency component contained in the random load, the power spectral density was introduced. The power spectral density S_i for a frequency f_i under the sinusoidal fluctuation can theoretically be given by $S_i = A^2 / f_i$, where A is the stress amplitude. Here, when the total power spectral density contained in one block is represented by S_0 , the ratio of power spectral density R_i is obtained by $R_i = S_i / S_0$ and the values of R_i for Type I wave are shown in Table 7. The constant values of m_p and $(\log C)_p$ in case of the random load which contains the various frequencies were calculated from the following equations by means of the weighted mean as shown in Table 5.

$$m_p = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n m_i R_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n R_i} \quad , \quad (\log C)_p = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (\log C)_i R_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n R_i} \quad (12)$$

The result of estimated S-N line for Type I wave is shown in Eq.(13).

$$\sigma^{13.905} \times N_f = 9.792 \times 10^{33} \quad (13)$$

Since not only the frequency but also the stress amplitude are changed at random for Type II wave, the equivalent stress amplitude was used in order to evaluate the amount of applied stress. The values of equivalent stress amplitude calculated by Eq.(8) are shown in Table 6. Experimental results of the fatigue life under Type I wave and Type II wave and the estimated S-N line of Type I are shown in Fig. 14. The fatigue life under program loads of Type I wave with various frequency could be estimated by using the weighted mean of the constants in S-N relationship. On the other hand, in the case of the changing both the stress amplitude and the frequency, the fatigue life could be estimated by using the equivalent stress amplitude in addition to that.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

An experimental investigation was performed to study the fatigue life estimation under various input waves, program loads and random loads. The test results showed that the effects of input wave type and stress pattern (High-Low, Low-High, Low-High-Low, Random) could be explained fairly well with the aid of r.m.s. peak stress value. Then, discussions were made on the validity of evaluating the fatigue life under the Gaussian narrow band random loads with the aid of equivalent stress amplitude based upon Miner's rule. Moreover, discussions were made on the effect of frequency dependency and it was shown that the fatigue life under program loads with various frequencies could be estimated by using the weighted mean of constants in S-N relationship.

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Table 1. Material of specimen.

Matrix	Polyester resin (Polylite FG-284)
Reinforcement	Satin woven glass cloth (SLS-212)
Catalizer	Methyl ethyl keton per oxide
Hardener	Cobalt naphthenate 0.6% solution

Table 2. Glass fiber content of the specimen and its static properties.

Weight content W_g	58.14 (%)
Volume content V_g	39.77 (%)
Tensile strength σ_t	298.4 (MPa)
Bending strength σ_b	430.0 (MPa)

Table 3. Values of constants in Eq.(1).

Wave type	m	C
Sin. wave	34.502	1.514×10^{74}
Triangular wave	41.154	7.528×10^{87}
Pulse wave	42.025	7.294×10^{86}

Fig. 1 Fatigue test specimen.

Fig. 2 S-N diagram for various input wave.

Fig. 3 P-S-N diagram (sinusoidal wave).

Fig. 4 Relation between r.m.s. peak stress value and fatigue life.

Fig. 5 Actually observed program loads.

Table 4. The assigned values of t/T for each stage i .

Stage i	t/T			
	Low-High	High-Low	Low-High-Low	Random
1	0.05	0.9	0.05	0.3
2	0.1	0.8	0.1	0.8
3	0.2	0.6	0.2	0.2
4	0.3	0.393	0.3	0.8
5	0.393	0.3	0.393	0.393
6	0.6	0.2	0.6	0.3
7	0.8	0.1	0.8	0.1
8	0.9	0.05	0.9	0.6
9			0.8	0.2
10			0.6	0.6
11			0.393	0.05
12			0.3	0.9
13			0.2	0.1
14			0.1	0.393

Table 5. Values of constants in Eq.(6).

Frequency f (Hz)	m	$\text{Log}C$
0.1	11.963	29.993
1	11.262	28.813
5	13.210	32.618
10	19.437	44.926
15	23.610	53.089
20	27.889	61.127

Fig. 6 Relation between r.m.s. peak stress value and fatigue life in program load test.

Fig. 7 P-S-N diagram (1 Hz).

Fig. 8 S-N diagrams for various kinds of frequency.

Fig.10 Power spectral density distribution.

RW1 wave

RW2 wave

Fig. 9 Actually observed random loads.

Fig.11 Relation between peak stress amplitude and fatigue life.

Fig.12 Relation between equivalent stress amplitude and fatigue life.

Table 6. Relation between frequency order, stress amplitude for each stage i and the value of equivalent stress amplitude σ_{eff} .

Stage i	f_i (Hz)	Stress amplitude σ_i (MPa)			
1	20	150	140	130	120
2	5	140	130	120	110
3	15	130	120	110	100
4	1	140	130	120	110
5	10	150	140	130	120
6	5	130	120	110	100
7	1	150	140	130	120
8	20	130	120	110	100
9	15	150	140	130	120
10	10	140	130	120	110
11	5	150	140	130	120
12	20	140	130	120	110
13	10	130	120	110	100
14	15	140	130	120	110
Equivalent stress amplitude σ_{eff} (MPa)		143.36	133.53	123.72	113.94

Type I wave

Type II wave

Fig.13 Actually observed program loads.

Table 7. Values of R_i for each frequency under Type I.

Frequency f_i (Hz)	Power spectral density ratio R_i
1	0.615
5	0.185
10	0.092
15	0.062
20	0.046

Fig.14 Relation between equivalent stress amplitude and fatigue life under random frequency.